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**INFLUENCE OF INTESTINAL MICROFLORA ON THE
DEVELOPMENT OF GALLSTONE DISEASE
(LITERATURE REVIEW)**

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Abstract: *gallstone disease is one of the most common diseases of the digestive system, which affects all segments of the population. Currently, gallstone disease is considered as a long, multi-stage process, in which the period of stone formation is preceded by changes in the metabolism and physicochemical properties of bile. However, among the numerous predisposing factors, insufficient attention is paid to the role of the infectious agent in the development of cholelithiasis. The analysis of the literature data showed that today there are various mechanisms for promoting enteric bacterial overgrowth in the development of cholelithiasis. First, with excessive bacterial growth, duodenobiliary reflux leads to infection of the biliary tract and the development of an inflammatory process in the gallbladder. Substances arising from the inflammatory process (proteins,*

mucus, desquamated epithelium) are the matrix on which the gallstone is formed. Secondly, the essential role of dysbiosis is traced in the violation of enterohepatic circulation of bile acids. A change in the ratio of conjugated and deconjugated bile acids contributes to the formation of lithogenic bile.

Keywords: *gallstone disease, microflora, bacteria, intestines, endotoxemia.*

Cholelithiasis (GSD) is one of the most common diseases of the digestive system, which affects all segments of the population [1, 2]. The incidence of gallstone disease in different countries (regions of the world) is 10-15% [3]. Currently, gallstones is considered as a long, multi-stage process, in which the period of stone formation is preceded by changes in the metabolism and physicochemical properties of bile. However, among the many contributing factors, insufficient attention is paid to the role of the infectious agent in the development of cholelithiasis.

Data from studies of contamination of the biliary tract with microflora in gallstones Biliary tract infection most often occurs enterally due to insufficiency of the sphincter structures of the biliary tract, on the one hand, and bacterial overgrowth in the small intestine, on the other hand [4].

Excessive growth of opportunistic bacteria in the intestine, their dissemination in the body against the background of a decrease in barrier and other protective factors leads to the ingress of agents into the biliary tract and the development of an inflammatory process. Opportunistic enterobacteriaceae colonize the biliary tract due to translocation from the large intestine against the background of dysbiotic disorders [5]. In this case, microorganisms sensitive to bile die, and resistant ones acquire the ability to colonize the corresponding biotope with the development of an infectious and inflammatory process [6]. It was found that bile, the wall of the gallbladder and gallstones in patients with various clinical forms of cholelithiasis are infected mainly by the microflora characteristic of the intestine. Among the microorganisms isolated from the gallbladder of patients with cholecystitis and gallstone disease, opportunistic enterobacteria,

E. coli, streptococcus, staphylococcus, typhoid bacillus, protozoa (lamblia) occupy the leading place [7]. At the same time, a significant prevalence of aerobic flora over anaerobic flora is observed. The most pronounced antibacterial activity of bile and bile acids against anaerobes (bacteroids, clostridia, lactobacilli), as well as gram-positive cocci (pneumococci, staphylococci). Gram-negative microorganisms are less susceptible to their action (*Salmonella*, *Shigella*, *Escherichia coli*) [6].

In patients with an increased risk of stone formation in the gallbladder and with cholelithiasis, according to the results of studying short-chain fatty acids in feces, a change in the qualitative composition of microflora was revealed, expressed in an increase in the activity of those genera of microorganisms that are involved in 7-alpha-dehydroxylation of bile acids, namely, aerobic microorganisms (in particular, *Escherichia coli*, (and anaerobes (some strains of the genera of bacteroids, clostridia, eubacteria).

There is evidence in the literature that a similar process of bacterial translocation is possible for other intestinal microorganisms - enterobacteria (*Klebsiella*, serration), pseudomonads, staphylococci, enterococci, etc. [6]. The pronounced resistance to bile in *E. coli* strains isolated in cholecystitis is an adaptive reaction that developed as a result of prolonged contact with bile. A relatively high level of resistance was shown by *E. coli* copstrains obtained during intestinal dysbiosis, which is due to the functioning of the "vicious circle", when bacteria from the intestine migrate to the portal veins, enter the liver, then into the bile ducts, interact with bile and again enter the intestines [8].

The overwhelming majority of literature sources provide data that in cholecystitis, regardless of the nature of the lesion, bacteriocholia is mainly caused by enterobacteria, among which *Escherichia coli* accounts for 30-57%. In addition to *Escherichia*, biliary cultures can be represented by other representatives of the Enterobacteriaceae family: *Klebsiella* (1-10%), *Proteus* (7-8%), *Enterobacter* (9.2%), etc. - up to 75% in total. The share of enterococci on average accounts for 10 to 27%, staphylococci -

from 9.7 to 16.25%, streptococci - from 7.3 to 12.5%. Less common are pseudomonads, yeast-like fungi [9]. Literature data [9, 10] indicate the predominance of intestinal bacteria in bile in patients with pathology of the hepatobiliary zone, although there are other results. For example, the work of K.I. Savitskaya et al. (2003) [11], which presented data on the release of gram-positive coccal flora from the bile of patients with chronic pancreatitis in 70% of cases.

According to the results of most bacteriological analyzes of bile, carried out for gallstones, in second place after enterobacteria are microbes of the genus *Enterococcus* [9], which are representatives of the normal microflora of the human digestive tract.

Among the cultures of strict anaerobes obtained from bile, non-spore-forming species predominate (89%), and in 11% of cases - clostridia [6]. Among anaerobic bilicures, representatives of the Bacteroidaceae family are more often determined, in 25% of cases *Bacteroides fragilis* (*B. Fragilis*) are represented. The proportion of anaerobic cocci (peptococci, peptostreptococci and anaerobic streptococci) can also be significant in this pathology, and is 21.4% of all anaerobic strains.

Bile can be one of the factors that regulate the microbial composition in the gallbladder, ducts, intestines, and thus form a certain microecology of the digestive tract [3]. A.V. Valyshev et al. (1996) [5] revealed the identity of pathogens isolated from feces and bile in 74% of cases, and the presence of persistence factors (antilysozyme, anti-interferon and anti-complementary signs) in isolated bacterial strains with intestinal dysbiosis and diseases of the biliary tract. This confirms the leading role of the intestinal microbiocenosis in the development of inflammatory processes in the hepatobiliary system and, as a consequence, the formation of lithogenic bile [12].

The main component of bile is primary bile acids cholic and chenodeoxycholic), which are synthesized in hepatocytes from cholesterol with the participation of the cholesterol-7 α -hydroxylase enzyme. Once in the ileum, approximately 85-90% of primary gallstone with the participation of intestinal microbiota

are deconjugated, absorbed and transported through the portal vein to hepatocytes, where they are again conjugated and incorporated into bile [1, 13]. It has been established that bacteroids and lactobacilli are involved in this process [14]. Approximately 5-10% of non-absorbed primary FAs enter the large intestine, where, under the influence of bacterial 7 α -dehydroxylase of gram-positive anaerobic bacteria (eubacteria and clostridia), secondary hydrophobic FAs (deoxycholic and lithocholic) are formed, which are absorbed, enter the liver and re-enter return conjugations in hepatocytes. In patients with gallstone disease, the transit time through the intestine is increased, which enhances the formation of deoxycholic acid as a result of bacterial metabolism. The increased concentration of secondary fatty acids in the gallbladder has a lithogenic effect.

Disturbance of enterohepatic circulation of bile acids is of great importance in the development of cholelithiasis [15, 16]. In patients with cholelithiasis and chronic acalculous cholecystitis, there was a violation of the enterohepatic circulation of bile acids of the fatty acid, manifested by a change in the exchange of cholic acid, cholesterol and phospholipids. This is due to an increase in the activity of anaerobic microorganisms participating in 7-alpha dehydroxylation of gallstone [17].

In patients with gallstone disease, a greater number of bacteria and 7-dehydroxylase activity are detected in intestinal aspirate from the ileum, combined with a higher pH in the colon and an increased transit time in the small and large intestine. Among the known causes of malabsorption of fatty acids, there is a prolongation of the intestinal transit period, which contributes to an increase in the time of bacterial conjugation even with a constant quantitative and qualitative composition of the microflora [18-20].

An important role in the violation of enterohepatic circulation of bile acids gallstone belongs to the acceleration of the intestinal passage time, which leads to an increase in gallstone excretion with feces and a decrease in their absorption [21]. On the other hand, there is evidence that a decrease in fatty acids decreases the antibacterial properties of bile. This promotes the activation of

opportunistic microorganisms and the development of bacterial overgrowth in the intestine. But the frequency and features of the occurrence of gallstone, as well as intestinal dysbiosis in cholelithiasis, remain insufficiently studied. To date, data have been accumulated that the intestinal microflora is capable of biotransformation of gallstone, cholesterol, and steroid hormones into various metabolites during the enterohepatic circulation of bile acids process [23].

Chronic biliary insufficiency, which leads to overgrowth of bacteria and premature deconjugation of fatty acids, which damage the mucous membrane of the small intestine and even the large intestine, has a special imprint on the course of gallstones. The inflammatory process in the mucous membrane of the small intestine leads to violations of the enterohepatic circulation of bile acids of the GI, while biliary insufficiency is aggravated. Under physiological conditions, the sterility of bile is provided by the antibacterial effect of fatty acids. In chronic biliary insufficiency, especially when combined with a reduced concentration and evacuation function of the gallbladder and dysfunction of the sphincter of Oddi, conditions are created to reduce the antibacterial properties of bile. At the stage of biliary sludge formation, biliary insufficiency is detected in 91.7% of cases (of which 54.5% are mild, and 45.5% are moderate) [18].

A decrease in the antibacterial properties of bile inevitably creates favorable conditions for the development of gallstone in the small intestine. More pronounced changes in the microflora of the small intestine occur with cholecystolithiasis. Due to a decrease in the protective function of the gallbladder, expressed in the bactericidal effect of bile, excessive bacterial growth occurs in the intestine of a patient with cholelithiasis, while the number of representatives of the obligate intestinal normal flora decreases and it is replaced by opportunistic bacteria. In biopsies of the mucous membrane of the duodenum in patients with cholelithiasis, signs of activation of opportunistic microflora with the release of up to 28 different genera of microorganisms are found. At the same time, hemolytic staphylococci (53%), bacteria of the Enterobacteriaceae family (69%), fungi of the genus

Candida (49%), bacteroids (47%) in the amount of 3.3-5.2 Ig KOE / g in combination of 2-7 cultures [19].

As shown by the studies carried out by Vakhrushev Ya.M. et al. (2017) [24], a biochemical study of bile revealed a significant decrease in the concentration of fatty acids in the gallbladder and hepatic portions of bile in patients with cholelithiasis compared with controls. Also, in patients with cholesterol, a tendency to an increase in cholesterol concentration and a significant decrease in the cholesterol coefficient in both the gallbladder and hepatic portions of bile were revealed. The study of individual gallstone fractions in patients with cholelithiasis showed a decrease in free (cholic, chenodeoxycholic, deoxycholic) and an increase in conjugated (glycocholic, glycodeoxycholic, taurocholic, taurodeoxycholic, ursodeoxycholic) gallstone in portions "B" and "C" bile in comparison with control. Disruption of the balance of free and conjugated fatty acids leads to the development of colloidal instability of bile, which is a prerequisite for the development of cholelithiasis. In a study by the same authors, the total content of fatty acids in the blood according to the results of mass spectrometry showed its decrease in patients with cholelithiasis in comparison with the control. In this case, multidirectional violations of the LC spectrum were noted. Thus, chenodeoxycholic and deoxycholic acids were reduced, while ursodeoxycholic, glycocholic, glycodeoxycholic, taurocholic and taurodeoxycholic acids were increased. The synthesis of gallstone from cholesterol occurs in the hepatocyte and includes 17 different enzymes that are located in the cytosol, endoplasmic reticulum, mitochondria, and peroxisomes [25]. It should be borne in mind that the synthesis of fatty acids is influenced not only by the state of the liver and the fatty acids themselves, which can, according to the principle of negative feedback, contribute to an increase or decrease in their content, but also cholesterol, thyroid hormones, glucocorticoids, insulin, circadian rhythms [13,25,26]. The small intestine is actively involved in maintaining gallstone homeostasis by synthesizing fibroblast growth factor-15 by enterocytes, which regulates a number of enzymes responsible for gallstone synthesis [13]. Changes in the gallstone composition

in the blood may be associated with an increase in gallstone absorption in the proximal small intestine. In patients with pre-stone stage of cholelithiasis, the development of bacterial overgrowth leads to disruption of the normal absorption of fatty acids in the distal ileum. In this case, premature deconjugation and absorption of fatty acids are characteristic [27, 28]. Against the background of the development of bacterial overgrowth, there is a decrease in free and an increase in conjugated fatty acids in bile. In addition, the development of bacterial overgrowth can serve as an initial link in the bacterial translocation mechanism [29]. There are microorganisms that are more prone to translocation due to their better ability to adhere to the intestinal epithelium (*Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella*, enterococci). This bacterial flora is able to penetrate even through the histologically normal mucous membrane of the intestinal wall, then entering the hepatobiliary system. It can be assumed that the detected the development of bacterial overgrowth in most patients with the pre-stone stage of cholelithiasis can be a source of bacteriocholia, and bacterial colonization of the extrahepatic biliary tract contributes to gallstones [30].

Lactobacillus and bacteroid enzymes are involved in the process of gallstone deconjugation in the distal ileum and proximal colon [31]. In 100% of patients with cholelithiasis, inoculation of feces revealed intestinal dysbiosis, while in the majority of patients (91%), various variants of combined disorders of the colon microflora are noted. To a greater extent, there was a decrease in the number of lactobacilli less than 107 CFU / g in 40.9% of patients with pre-stone stage of cholelithiasis. An increase in the proportion of lactose-negative and hemolytic *Escherichia coli* (up to 28.6% and 18.2%, respectively) was also revealed against the background of a decrease in full-fledged *Escherichia coli* (in 31.8% of patients). Consequently, against the background of the development of bacterial overgrowth and colonic dysbiosis, significant changes occur in the deconjugation of gallstone, which leads to a violation of the ratio of conjugated and deconjugated gallstone in bile and blood. Violation of enterohepatic circulation of bile acids leads to

a decrease in the gallstone content in the intestine. Malabsorption syndrome develops, the composition of the intestinal microflora is disturbed, ethanol and organic acids are formed in excess, the pH of the chyme decreases and the deconjugation of fatty acids increases. The consequence is the progression of the development of bacterial overgrowth, the formation of an increased amount of endotoxins, their entry into the liver and the development of systemic inflammation [32]. That is, dysbiosis leads to a violation of the enterohepatic circulation of bile acids of the gallstone, and a decrease in the intake of gallstone in the intestine aggravates the dysbiosis.

Thus, the small intestine is an important link in the violation of the enterohepatic circulation of bile acids of the gallstone. An increase in the absorption of prematurely deconjugated fatty acids in the proximal part of the small intestine accelerates the time it takes for fatty acids to return to the liver, as a result of which their synthesis in hepatocytes and excretion into bile decreases. As a result of the development of bacterial overgrowth in the distal ileum and colonic dysbiosis, significant changes occur in the deconjugation of gallstone, which leads to a violation of the ratio of gallstone fractions in the blood and bile.

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